
PHILOSOPHY IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Philosophy the "love of wisdom," is a rational, systematic, and critical inquiry into fundamental thoughts about existence, knowledge, values, reason, mind, and language. Using logical thought and reflection, Philosophy aims to deepen one's understanding and persuade wiser thought and action in all aspects of life. On the other hand, Literature is a form of human expression in a well – organized systematic writing in the form of novels, plays, and poems, which expresses complex ideas and emotions through creative and skillful use of language. Philosophy of Literature uses philosophical methods to study literature whereas, Philosophical for Literature uses literary forms to explore philosophical ideas. Both Philosophy and literature grapple with fundamental questions about morality, justice, knowledge, and the human condition, in different modes. Works of literature, through characters and plot, offer case studies for exploring complex ethical and rational issues that are the reflection of philosophical thought. This paper discusses on the influences of philosophy on literature from different countries and focuses on how the philosophical ideas guide readers to regain wisdom and eternal truth after reading any form of literature.

Key Words: Indian literature, Greek Literature, American Literature and English Literature and German Literature.

Philosophy in Indian Literature

Indian literature has philosophical ideas in all forms of its literature. The great Indian epics Ramayana and Mahabharata speak on different paths of dharma, the meaning for our

existence which suits not only for an individual alone but for the entire humanity. The ethical path and spiritual guidance in both the epics, through multiple characters in complicated situations help to attain wisdom and to retain peace and harmony in the society. Both the epics portray God as characters to glorify dharma and karmic duties of an individual. The whole text of Bhagavat Gita with its 700 slokas arranged under different yogas or chapters are the pathways for human beings to furnish a well nourished ethical world. Apart from these epics, the different writers like Dr. Radhakrishnan, Sri Aurobindho, Swami Vivekanda drags the whole western world to replenish their life in Indian dharmic system. The Indian philosophy goes to the extent of glorifying and regulating sexual pleasures in Kamasutra and materialistic gains through war fields in Arthasasthra. The great Noble Prize winner Rabindranath Tagore's Gitanjali explores themes of Spirituality, Devotion to God, and the profound connection between the Divine and Human life.

India being a state of different culture and language has too many philosophical writers in literature and great philosophical writers in Tamil literature includes Thiruvalluvar, Subramania Bharathiar, Kannadasan Thirumoolar etc. These classic writers wrote on all facts of life with deep knowledge on psychology, Yoga practice, Politics, Economics, Theology and even on war tactics. The philosophical concepts in their writings give the readers a deep knowledge on the complications of life and guide them in their routine life, to face any situations. The literary forms also give pleasures of relishing life with inner satisfaction and peace. An ordinary man in India promptly understands his duties as a son, as a father, as a citizen and as a husband to pursue his life with entire satisfaction and happiness. Also simple narration and plots in a novel, short story also preach Philosophy to people. Tamil Novel writers like Asokamithran, Prabanjan, Indira Sowndrarajan, Balakumaran have special feature of writing philosophical novels.

Philosophical writings in Greek Literature

Greek Literature has great Philosophers like Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, and their contribution to ancient Greek people are immense as it promotes democracy, liberation and growth of knowledge among the citizens. Socrates known as “the Father of Philosophy” propagates the idea that ‘an unexamined life is not worth living’ and advocated for self- reflection and critical enquiry to achieve virtue and happiness. The teaching of Socrates is written by Plato, his student, who started a school named “Academia” to teach skillful children. Plato’s Cave allegory is an example for effect of education and liberation for individuals to get better and secured life. It represents a world of Illusion and a world of truth and knowledge. The allegory of caves with picturesque representation make the readers to acknowledge and judge the true power of knowledge. Aristotle’s theory of Mimesis posts that art is an act of imitation of life actions. Aristotle also developed Logic, establishing the principles of Syllogism, which forms the basis for reasoning. He also proposed the Golden mean which is a mean point between two extreme vices. Epicurus preached the Epicurean philosophy of “Eat, drink and be happy” for acquiring entire tranquility and happiness of life.

Philosophy in English literature:

English being a universal language has helped us to read different countries philosophical concepts in English and has helped in understanding the concepts clearly. The plays of Shakespeare exposed all human characters and focus on different philosophical theories. The crucial role of human life is expressed as follows

“As flies are to wanton boys are we to gods, they kill us for their sports “(King Lear- Act IV, Scene I).

“We are such stuff/As dreams are made on, and our little life is rounded with a sleep”
(The Tempest Act IV, Scene 1)

The works of Francis Bacon have the crux of life when it shared the quotes “Knowledge is Power”. He believed that Knowledge gained through observation and experimentation could empower Individuals and societies by enabling decision making, problem solving and control over natural calamities and make their life more secured. John Pilgrim’s The Pilgrim’s Progress marks the human progress in search of God through the refinement of soul and moral means. John Ruskin’s Utopia suggested for a better world with guild principles and social justice. The 18th century England witnessed an industrial revolution and shift in cultural behaviors of its citizens. Philosophers like John Locke, David Hume, Adam Smith influenced literature with their morals. Literature became a vehicle for moral instructions, social criticisms and rational thinking. Writers like Henry Fielding, Samuel Johnson and Jonathan Swift used poetry, essays and novels as philosophical instruments to explore the nature of Man. The Absurd plays highlights the absurdity and at the same time analyzed the entire meaning of life is to understand and guide others.

Philosophy in American Literature

Philosophy in American Literature can be understood by reading Enlightenment writers like Benjamin Franklin, Thomas Paine, Jefferson, Emerson, David Thoreau and Nathaniel Hawthorne. Being a land of multi cultured society, the American writers questioned morality, destiny and Nihilism. But the Transcendentalism movement in America emphasized on Individualism, Self-reliance and the innate goodness of humanity and nature. The American great writers like Walt Whitman. Robert Frost reflects themes on Individualism, nature and the divine in everything around them. Its rise was a protest against the state of Intellectualism and spirituality at that time. The idea of intuitive thought and a direct knowledge of inner feelings was a superior form of knowledge. The concept of Existentialism, Post structuralism and Post modernism questioned the universal truth and the meaning of existence. The inherent value of

the individual and a belief in interconnectedness of life are greatly portrayed in American Literature.

Philosophy in German Literature

The prominent figures in German philosophers are Immanuel Kant, George Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Karl Marx, and Friedrich Nietzsche. The German thinkers contributed ideas on Transcendental Idealism, Absolute Idealism and dialectical process, Communism, Ubermensch or Self-Creation to the humanity. Arthur Schopenhauer is noted for his noumenal and phenomenal world and his pessimism theory. Georg Wilhelm Fredrich Hegel extends widely from various topics like Epistemology, Ontology and Political Philosophy. His friend Karl Marx contributed The Communist Manifesto which became a great source to unite the world laborers and form Communism. It was a revolution in the lives of many poor laborers to overcome their ruling class and get united under one name as laborers. Marx is also celebrated as one of the principal architect of modern sociology for his heterodox theories of labour and capital. The Capitalist movement developed out of the intellectual currents of the enlightenment and the revolutionary politics of that era. Friedrich Nietzsche, Friedrich Engels are some other philosophers whose thoughts provoked rationalism and pessimism among people and help people to overcome their life with systematic approach of life.

Literature and Philosophy are two wings of human thought. Philosophy portrays truth through reasoning while Literature does the same through stories, characters and imagination. When Philosophical concepts find a place in Literature they give explicit knowledge and energy and boost the readers to understand it better. This fusion has guided mankind for centuries, teaching morals, values, making reforms and has strengthened the society far better than anything. The philosophical concepts like Existentialism, Nihilism, Stoicism, Epicureanism, Aesthetics, Marxism and Transcendentalism have their identity

among the learning community of people, through various forms of literature, better than mere philosophical concepts. Literature has conveyed enduring wisdom and has become a bridge between thought process and its impact ensuring that Philosophical concepts benefits not only the mind but also the heart and action of the readers.

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